

Secondary amines : Synthesis and effect of length of spacer linking two phenyl rings on biological activity

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Abstract : *N*-Benzyl benzylamines (1a-11a) and *N*-benzyl anilines (1b-11b) were synthesized by sodium borohydride reduction of aldimines of benzylamine and aniline respectively. The products were characterized on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral studies and screened for antifungal potential against four fungi and evaluated for nematocidal activity against two nematodes. The former compounds were found to be more effective as compared to the latter thus indicating an enhancement of biological activity due to introduction of an extra methylene group between two phenyl rings of aromatic secondary amines.

Keywords : *N*-Benzyl benzylamines, *N*-benzyl anilines, antifungal potential, nematocidal activity.

Introduction

In an earlier communication we have reported the synthesis of aldimines of benzylamine and aniline and the effect of introduction of an extra methylene group between two phenyl rings of aromatic aldimines on biological activity¹. In continuation of our work on the factors²⁻⁴ which determine the biological activity, this paper describes the synthesis of *N*-benzyl benzylamines and *N*-benzyl anilines, their characterization and the effect of spacer linking the two phenyl rings on antifungal potential and nematocidal activity.

The reduction of benzalbenzylamine and its *C*-phenyl derivatives¹ with sodium borohydride in methanol at 60–70 °C resulted in the formation of products **1a-11a** which have been characterized as *N*-benzyl benzylamine and its *N*-benzyl derivatives on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral studies. The IR spectra of compounds **1a-11a** lacked the absorption band at ~1620 cm⁻¹ assigned to >C=N- linkage but contained band at ~3350 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of N-H group. The PMR spectra of the products in CDCl₃ contained in addition to signals due to the presence of functional group in the respective secondary amine, a one proton singlet at δ ~4.2 indicating the presence of secondary amine proton. For instance, the PMR spectrum of *N*-benzyl benzylamine (**1a**) contained a singlet at δ 3.8 for protons of two methylene groups and a multiplet between δ 7.0–7.9 for ten aromatic protons and one proton broad signal at δ 4.1 for

amine proton thus justifying the presence of 15 protons in the molecule. *N*-Benzyl anilines (**1b-11b**) were similarly synthesized as a result of sodium borohydride reduction of benzalanilines¹. The products were confirmed on the basis of elemental analysis, m.p. determination and spectral studies^{5,6}.

N-Benzyl benzylamines (**1a-11a**) and *N*-benzyl anilines (**1b-11b**) were screened *in vitro* for antifungal potential against *Alternaria alternata*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Myrothecium roridum* and *Colletotrichum capsici* by spore germination inhibition method⁷. The results have been expressed in terms of ED₅₀ values (Table 1).

All the test *N*-benzyl benzylamines (**1a-11a**) and *N*-benzyl anilines (**1b-11b**) possessed ED₅₀ values less than 1000 ppm against *A. alternata* but ED₅₀ values in case of former compounds were much lower than that of the latter and the most effective test compound against the fungus was found to be *N*-(4-methoxybenzyl)benzylamine (**4a**) with ED₅₀ value of 80 ppm. Two more compounds (**3a** and **5a**) also showed promising potential with ED₅₀ value of 160 and 140 ppm respectively. All the test *N*-benzyl benzylamines had ED₅₀ values less than 1000 ppm against *F. oxysporum* and three of these (**3a**, **4a**, **5a**) possessed promising potency with ED₅₀ values less than 200 ppm against the test fungus. Seven of the test *N*-benzyl anilines showed moderate activity against *F. oxysporum*.

The test compound **3a**, **4a** and **5a** possessed promis-

Table 1. Antifungal potential of *N*-benzyl benzylamines and *N*-benzyl anilines

Compd.	ED ₅₀ value (ppm) against							
	<i>A. alternata</i>		<i>F. oxysporum</i>		<i>M. roridum</i>		<i>C. capsici</i>	
	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b
1	410	450	670	730	510	670	430	480
2	400	390	685	725	340	360	90	415
3	150	360	160	335	180	170	70	95
4	80	640	160	720	160	305	38	65
5	140	590	170	685	145	*	35	680
6	360	610	370	810	360	720	87	710
7	390	600	720	*	675	885	85	365
8	390	620	705	*	330	*	310	315
9	340	670	360	765	330	*	310	605
10	290	580	720	*	330	640	340	870
11	340	570	330	*	210	830	310	920

*More than 1000 ppm; a : *N*-benzyl benzylamines, b : *N*-benzyl anilines.

ing potential against *M. roridum* with ED₅₀ value of 180, 160 and 145 ppm, respectively. Out of eight *N*-benzyl anilines which showed ED₅₀ value less than 1000 ppm against *M. roridum*, only one compound (3b) was found to possess promising activity against *M. roridum* with ED₅₀ value of 170 ppm. Six of *N*-benzyl benzylamines and two of *N*-benzyl anilines possessed ED₅₀ values less than 100 ppm against *C. capsici*.

The synthesized compounds were evaluated for nematocidal activity against *Ditylenchus myceliophagus* and *Caenorhabditis elegans* following *in vitro* water screen-

ing technique⁸. All the test *N*-benzyl benzylamine (1a-11a) induced more than 50 per cent mortality of *D. myceliophagus* whereas only three *N*-benzyl anilines showed more than 50 per cent mortality at 1000 ppm. Same trend was observed at lower concentrations of 500 and 250 ppm (Table 2). All the test *N*-benzyl benzylamines and eight *N*-benzyl anilines inflicted more than 50 per cent mortality of *C. elegans* at 1000 ppm. The most potent compound against *D. myceliophagus* and *C. elegans* was found to be *N*-(3-nitrobenzyl)benzylamine (10a) and *N*-(3-methoxy-4-hydroxybenzyl)benzylamine (7a) with per

Table 2. Nematicidal activity of *N*-benzyl benzylamines and *N*-benzyl anilines

Compd.	<i>In vitro</i> per cent mortality against											
	<i>D. myceliophagus</i>						<i>C. elegans</i>					
	1000		500		250		1000		500		250	
	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b
1	88	37	79	26	45	15	81	81	63	76	45	43
2	78	56	44	43	29	17	76	75	45	48	32	24
3	72	48	66	21	55	14	79	67	61	41	32	29
4	82	78	76	67	52	34	65	67	45	43	30	32
5	56	22	27	18	20	9	76	48	37	30	22	20
6	73	46	54	33	23	16	78	73	65	61	27	19
7	63	32	50	23	20	13	87	55	70	32	61	21
8	68	52	62	37	41	23	67	59	56	37	38	26
9	78	22	54	18	30	10	50	45	22	20	19	12
10	89	34	75	23	66	19	79	52	50	29	18	10
11	75	33	51	25	30	20	85	43	63	32	44	21
Control	3.7	3.7	3.7	3.7	3.7	3.7	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3

a : *N*-Benzyl benzylamines, b : *N*-benzyl anilines.

R : H; 4-Cl; 4-OH; 4-OCH₃; 3-OCH₃, 4-OCH₃; 2-OCH₃, 5-OCH₃; 3-OCH₃, 4-OH; 3-OC₂H₅; 4-OH; 3-OCH₃, 4-OCH₃, 5-OCH₃; 3-NO₂ and 4-F

Fig. 1. The reaction sequence.

cent mortality of 66 and 51 at 250 ppm respectively.

A comparative study of biological activity of *N*-benzyl benzylamines (1a-11a) and *N*-benzyl anilines (1b-11b) has revealed that the former compounds are much more effective as compared to the latter indicating an enhancement in biological activity due to introduction of an extra methylene group between two phenyl rings of aromatic secondary amines.

Experimental

All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis and the melting points are uncorrected.

Synthesis of *N*-benzyl benzylamines : Benzalbenzylamine or its *C*-phenyl derivative (0.01 mol) was dissolved in methanol (50 ml) and the solution was heated to 60–70 °C. To this solution then added NaBH₄ (2.0 g in 2 ml of 2 *N* sodium hydroxide diluted to 20 ml with water) dropwise with constant stirring at a rate of 0.5 ml per min. After complete addition of NaBH₄, the solution was further stirred for 1 h at room temperature and allowed to stand overnight. The excess of the solvent was then distilled off and the contents were cooled, diluted with water (100 ml) and extracted with chloroform. Evaporation of the solvent after drying (Na₂SO₄) gave the respective crude product. The solid products were recrystallized from methanol and liquid products were chromatographed over alumina to get the respective secondary amine with m.p. (°C) and % yield. **1a** (30, 45); **2a** (155, 55); **3a** (100, 75); **4a** (56, 70); **5a** (oil, 75); **6a** (oil, 60); **7a** (178, 80); **8a** (77, 85); **9a** (oil, 70); **10a** (67, 80) and **11a** (62, 53).

Following the above procedure *N*-benzyl anilines (1b-11b) were prepared by reducing benzalaniline and its *C*-phenyl derivatives with m.p. (°C) and % yield : **1b** (43, 73); **2b** (76, 55); **3b** (oil, 80); **4b** (45, 85); **5b** (87, 59); **6b** (oil, 57); **7b** (250, 65); **8b** (82, 70); **9b** (135, 60); **10b** (90, 74) and **11b** (102, 62).

***In vitro* screening for antifungal potential** : The stock solution of 2000 ppm of each compound was prepared by dissolving each chemical (20 mg) in absolute alcohol (0.5 ml) and the volume was made to 10 ml with sterilized distilled water. The required dilutions were subsequently made from the stock solution by adding sterilized distilled water. Small droplets (0.02 ml) of spore suspension in equal quantity with solution of the test compound were seeded in the cavities of cavity slides. These slides were placed in petriplates lined with moist filter paper and incubated at 25 ± 1 °C for 24 h. The germination of spores was recorded and per cent spore germination inhibition was determined from which ED₅₀ values were calculated.

***In vitro* testing for nematicidal activity** : About 100 nematodes of each genera were exposed to 2 ml solution of the test compound at concentration of 1000, 500 and 250 ppm and observations for the number of living or dead nematodes were recorded after an interval of 96 h. The immobile nematodes with a definite posture were recorded as dead.

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